

Pedogenesis in rice growing hydric soils of Majuli river island, Assam, India

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Abstract : The elemental composition of four representative rice growing hydric soils in wetlands of Majuli islands were studied in relation to morphology and particle size by developing colour indices and element to clay ratio method. These texturally contrast and neutral to slightly alkaline rice growing soils showed striking difference in distribution of total calcium and low contents with serious loss of total iron and manganese in channel fills and old floodplains due to prolonged saturation. The change of soil moisture regime in alluvial plains, accelerates the leaching and loss of iron and manganese oxides from surface horizons and decrease in clay by lateral movement and ferrolysis processes that have favoured formation of iron-enriched subsurface horizons in paddy soils. An average linkage method was employed to workout chemical affinity and variability of soil properties among clusters. The cluster data showed that clay and bulk density are least variable whereas K, Ca, Fe and Mn are highly variable among clusters indicating the usefulness in delineating boundaries across landscapes of floodplain wetlands in the river island.

Keywords : Geochemistry, Majuli river island, hydric soils, element to clay ratio.

Introduction

A comprehensive characterization of alluvium derived soils in Majuli river island were made on 1:50000 scale and reported the occurrence of hydric soils¹. The morphology and physico-chemical characteristics of wide spread aquepts and fluvents in Brahmaputra valley were reported²⁻⁴. These are hydromorphic soils containing less clay and with a seasonally fluctuating pH in the surface horizon and occur extensively on the seasonally flooded landscapes⁵. These soils have stratified textures, abundance of free carbonates and high organic carbon in surface layers⁶. Soil colour was used as an indicator of redox processes⁷ but often misleading because of parent materials⁸ or organic carbon or oxide coatings⁹, relict redoximorphic features¹⁰ and elemental translocations under acid environments¹¹. The soil indicators of evolutionary changes in paddy environment are changes in soil Eh values, clay content and iron oxides because they all have substantial impact on soil quality as well as on rice production¹². The critical Eh-value for Fe reduction and consequent dissolution is 100 mV at pH 7 but vary in the critical redox values for Fe transformation¹³. It was reported that DCB-extractable iron (Fed) and its ratio

with total iron (Fet) (i.e. Fed/Fet) increase with the length of paddy cultivation¹² and total Fe content is higher in paddy soils than in non-paddy soils¹⁴. The total Fe and Mn are high in gleyed B horizons as compared to surface puddle Ap horizons and are related to silt and clay distribution in Disang Valley of Sibsagar district¹⁵.

These soils have variable groundwater influence and wide spread stratification of parent material. These soils reflect the translocation processes of soil solid and liquid phase¹⁶. A ratio method (volumetric approach) considering element to clay was employed to workout losses and gains^{17,18}. Although, the nature of parent material influence on elemental composition was reported¹⁹⁻²¹, but the exact role of pedogenesis in controlling potential nutrient reserves in relation to landscapes is not clearly understood. Similarly little information is available about elemental associations with redoximorphic features and particle size distribution. Hence, the present investigation was therefore undertaken with the objective of examining the relation of elemental composition of hydric soils in relation to morphology and particle size distribution and application of ratio method for calculating losses and gains of elements in Majuli river island.

Materials and methods :

Study area and soil profiles : The Majuli island (93°30'–94°35' E and 26°50' and 27°10' N) is situated in north of Jorhat district. The elevation on the island varies from 60 to 85 m above mean sea level. The island is bounded by three important rivers viz. Kherkutia Suti, the Subansiri in the north and the Brahmaputra river in the south. Four representative profiles such as Kamalabari on active flood plains (P1), Adielengi on old flood palins (P2), Sonaribari on natural levees (P3) and Boritika on channel fills (P4) were chosen for geochemical interpretations of hydric soils in the present study. On alluvial plains, these soils show a distinct evolutionary direction on iron/manganese dynamics in relation to continuously submerged conditions (P2 and P3) to alternate reduced and oxidised conditions creating endoaquic (Controlled by ground water saturation²²). Horizon wise soil samples were collected for these selected soil series for laboratory analysis. Particle size distribution (International pipette method), pH (1 : 2 soil water ratio), organic carbon (wet oxidation method), exchangeable bases extracted from in IN neutral NH₄OAc by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer model), CEC by distillation method and total elements in triacid digestion^{23,24}.

(i) *Colour index :* The munsell colour notation was converted to a single numerical colour index as per the scheme of Evans and Franzmeier⁷. The scheme consists of three steps (1) condense the munsell notations of soil colour into a single number, (2) apply that number to the various parts of features of a soil horizon to obtain a number of that horizon and (3) integrate horizon values into a single number to represent the pedon.

$C1 = (i_{i=1}^m \Sigma X \text{ matrix, } i \text{ C matrix, } i) + (i_{i=1}^n \Sigma X \text{ mottles, } i \text{ C mottles, } i)$.

$C2 = [i_{i=1}^m \Sigma X \text{ matrix, } i (45- H \text{ matrix, } I + (C \text{ matrix, } i)] + [(i_{i=1}^n \Sigma X \text{ mottles, } I 20(45- H \text{ mottle} + C \text{ mottle, } i)]$

where X = abundance (Fraction), C = munsell chroma, m = total number of matrix colors, n = total number of redox concentration and depletion colors described, H is function of munsell hue rated as : 10R = 10, 2.5YR = 12.5, 5YR = 15.....2.5Y = 22.5, 5Y = 25..... and 5BG = 45, abundance assigned values (few = 0.01, common = 0.11, many = 0.35).

(ii) *Mass balance using ratio method :* The ratio method based on volumetric approach was employed (Fine earth) to calculate masses of pedogenic Fe, Mn, K, Ca and P and clay for a ground surface of 1 m² down to the upper boundary of the C horizon or any arbitrary depth (1 m)¹⁷. Relative losses and gains of the element under consideration can be achieved by comparing the element : clay ratio in a pedon (=P ratio) with the element : clay ratio of parent material (=C ratio).

$$P \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{Element mass in the fine earth of a pedon} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \right)}{\text{Clay mass in the fine earth of a pedon} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \right)}$$

$$C \text{ ratio} = \frac{\text{Element mass in the fine earth of a C horizon} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \right)}{\text{Clay mass in the fine earth of a C horizon} \left(\frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^2} \right)}$$

The relative changes between soil and parent material was calculated as follows :

$$\text{Relative change (\%)} = \frac{P \text{ ratio} - C \text{ ratio}}{C \text{ ratio}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

Soil morphology and colour index values : Four hydric soils on four distinct fluvial land forms displayed horizon sequences of Ap-AC-C in Kamalabari (P1) on active floodplains with dark grey loamy textural sequence but have Ap-Bw-BC-C sequence in Adielengi (P2) on old flood plains with grey to dark grey silt loam to silty clay loam textures, Ap-B/A-Bw-BC sequence in Sonaribari (P3) on natural levees with olive grey (5Y5/2) to dark grey to dark greyish brown B horizons with silt loam textures and yellowish brown mottles and Ap-C1-2Bw1-2Bw2-C2 sequence in Boritika (P4) with dark grey to grey silty clay loam to sand textures. The hydric soils in Majuli island have displayed stripped zones or horizons of Fe, Mn due to reduced soluble forms under anaerobic condi-

tions¹⁵. The formulae of colour indexes as proposed to relate soil wetness and aeration characteristics by Evans and Franzmeier⁷ was used to calculate hue (C1) and chroma (C2) indices (Table 1). The data shows that the dark grey to dark reddish brown Kamalabari soils on active flood plains (P1) have decreasing trends of hue index (0.35 to 0.11) with little changes in chroma index (9.1 to 9.5). This soil has loamy with chroma 2 or less without any redox depletions. The grey Adielengi soil on old flood plains (P2) have low hue index (0.11) in upper 34 cm but increased to 0.55 in brown B horizons. This soil has sandy gleyed matrix in C horizons and chroma 1 or 2. This soil has low chroma index with little changes (2.3 to 2.97). The Sonaribari soil on natural levees (P3) have stratified textures with olive grey to dark greyish brown matrix and brown mottles from 38 to 90 cm. The hue index have a value of 0.7 in 30 cm surface layers but decreased to 0.11 in C horizons. The chroma index varies from 2.1 to 2.98 with depth. The Boritka soil on channel fills (P4) have dark grey to dark greyish brown matrix with chroma 1 or 2. This soil has 0.11 to 0.22 hue index and 2.25 to 2.36 chroma index with slight changes. The hue index has strong positive relation with Fe (0.43*) and Mn contents (0.42*) where as chroma index has a negative weak relation with Fe (-0.32) and Mn (-0.42). This colour index had a non linear relationship with time of saturation²⁵. Such kind of relations were reported in hydric soils of Brahmaputra valley by Bhaskar *et al.*¹⁸.

It has been long documented that the soil colour patterns are related to saturated conditions and microbial activity that depletes oxygen²⁶ where as redoximorphic features as marked by redox reactions of C, Mn, Fe and S in seasonally saturated soils by their loss or gain of pigmentation as compared with matrix and have depletions of iron loss with chroma ≤ 2 , value 4 or more in majuli soils under study where iron, manganese and perhaps clay have stripped from the area^{1,9}. The soil quality morphological index (SQMI) determined from near surface properties (30 cm) in combination of texture, structure, consistence, dry crust strength, thickness and macropores and cracks²⁷ provides a relative ranking of optimal physical conditions for root growth and development and free movement of water and air in the pedosphere. In this index, higher the value, better the soil quality²⁸. The soils on the levee have best quality

having the highest index value (SQMI = 3.52), followed by those on a terrace and least being those of upland²⁹. It implies that soils of the levee have the best soil physical fertility which according to Eneje *et al.*³⁰ is necessary for sustaining long-term crop production. In the latest version of fertility capability classification, proposed the modifiers such as "g⁺" to indicate prolonged waterlogging; with no evidence of mottles (P1, P2 and P4) indicative of Fe³⁺ compounds in the top 50 cm and includes paddy rice soils with slower soil N mineralization and Zn deficiencies in rice³¹. The hue index may be considered as quality indicator by linking with paddy cultivation history and yield trends over years in the region.

Particle size distribution and chemical properties :

The Kamalabari soil on active flood plains (P1) have 40 to 86% sand, 38 to 52% silt and 7 to 19% clay. The Adielengi soil on old flood plains (P2) shows gradational increase of sand from 14 to 96%, decrease of silt from 74 to 1.3% and bulged distribution of clay from 11% in Ap horizon to 33 to 21% in Bw horizons and 5 to 9% in C horizons. Sonaribari soil on natural levees (P3) have sand content of 1 to 46%, silt of 44 to 77% and duplex negative distribution of clay content of 9.5 to 34.5%. The cambic B horizons have more than 50% silt and 30.5% clay where as sand dominant in C horizons (78 to 93%). The high inflections of sand silt ratios with depth indicate textural contrast in soils of Brahmaputra as reported by many workers^{2,3,18,32}. High silt content is the characteristic feature in flood plains of Brahmaputra valley¹ and in Meghna flood plains of Bangladesh⁵. Based on weighted mean of silt content, the studied soils show the following gradation along the landscape : as Sonaribari (P3, 69.93%) > Kamalabari (P1, 33.17%) > Boritika (P4, 27.45%) > Adieleng (P2, 19.12%) whereas clay gradation follows : Sonaribari (P3, 17.21%) > Boritika (P4, 16.43%) > Adielengi (P2, 10.48%) and Kamalabari (P1, 9.75%). The young paddy growing Kamalabari series (P1) with A-C horizons have a lithological discontinuity at about 61 cm below the surface where gleyic horizon appears. Gleyic horizon is very coarse in texture and had only about 4.5% clay. It is clear that the seasonal flood deposits on active flood plains raise the profile bed and frees the soil above the influence of the gleyic horizon. The differences in clay content of B horizons are related to history of paddy cultivation and variability in depositions

of river sediments on analogous landscape positions^{15,33}. The high clay content (21 to 35%) in B horizons of Adielengi (P2, Table 1)) and Boritika (P4) is due to deposition of suspended fine materials from runoff whereas decreasing clay in B horizons of Sonaribari (P4, from 9.5 to 16.5%) is due to ferrollysis that destroys clay containing iron during reduction and oxidation cycles³⁴. The seasonal floods and drainage in moderately acid to neutral environments usually favour ferrollysis. The causes for particle size variations in paddy soils include ploughing, puddling, flooding and drainage that accelerates downward mechanical movement of particles resulting to texturally contrast subsoils³⁵. All soils are neutral to slightly alkaline except Kamalabari soil (P1) with moderately acid to neutral and increasing trend up to a certain depth. For

rice production, this is a suitable range, however, upon reduction of the (top) soil, the pH tends to change towards neutral (pH 6.5 to 7.0). Most plant nutrients are most readily available for uptake by roots in a slightly-acid to near-neutral environment. This increase in pH with depth is a common feature in most of the surface-water gley soils where ferrollysis is a common soil forming process. Ponnampuruma³⁶ noted that acidification of topsoil (P1) is caused by continual displacement of bases by ferrous iron during the anaerobic or reduction phase associated with annual flooding. The organic carbon varies from 9.7 g/kg (P2) to 19.5 g/kg (P3) in Ap horizons but decreased to 0.6 g/kg in C horizons (Table 1). Low organic carbon content is possibly due to rapid decomposition of organic matter under hyperthermic temperature

Table 1. Selected hydric soil characteristics in Majuli island

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Colour index		Particle size (<2 mm)			Sand/silt	pH	OC (g/kg)	CEC cmol (+) kg ⁻¹	Elemental composition						
		C1	C2	Sand	Silt	Clay					K	Na	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn
(P1) Kamalabari series – Humaqueptic fluvaquents																	
0–19	Ap	0.32	9.1	42.7	38.3	19.0	1.11	5.9	12.2	12.6	3.4	1.2	2.7	30.1	0.37	28	109
19–39	AC	0.35	9.1	40.4	43.1	16.5	0.94	6.9	4.8	12.3	1.8	0.9	2.1	33.2	0.38	29	110
39–61	C1	0.22	9.45	40.4	52.6	7.0	0.77	7.0	1.9	10.2	1.8	0.9	3.2	32.0	0.51	27	117
61–89	C2	0.11	9.1	49.5	42.0	8.5	1.18	7.1	2.5	11.2	1.7	0.9	3.0	31.1	0.48	25	109
89–130	C3	0.11	9.1	86.0	9.5	4.5	9.1	7.2	0.8	7.61	1.3	0.9	3.2	23.1	0.40	14	116
(P2) Adielengi – Typic Endoaquepts																	
0–13	Ap	0.11	2.31	14.7	74.3	11.0	0.19	7.1	9.7	11.1	8.8	2.5	8.5	38.3	0.64	39	77
13–34	Bw1	0.11	2.31	15.7	51.3	33.0	0.31	6.8	16.7	14.1	13.9	5.4	3.6	44.1	0.70	42	94
34–60	Bw2	0.55	2.70	22.4	56.6	21.0	0.40	7.0	5.8	12.5	9.4	2.8	4.1	41.5	0.81	44	81
60–98	C1	0.22	2.97	75.0	16.0	9.0	4.69	7.2	1.4	7.89	3.9	1.7	3.7	28.5	0.56	23	55
98–225	C2	0.11	2.86	96.3	1.5	5.0	74.1	7.2	1.4	3.48	2.1	1.5	2.6	14.6	0.26	5	30
(P3) Sonaribari series – Fluventic Endoaquepts																	
0–13	Ap	0.70	2.42	1.6	63.9	34.5	0.03	6.7	19.5	17.5	10.7	2.65	5.90	45.1	0.65	50	104
13–31	B/A	0.70	2.42	1.0	78.5	20.5	0.01	7.7	10.2	14.2	10.6	2.80	10.4	45.5	0.76	48	101
31–38	Bw1	0.35	2.31	11.9	74.6	13.5	0.16	7.7	5.0	11.7	7.5	1.95	9.8	41.35	0.71	42	97
38–47	Bw2	0.70	2.70	46.3	44.2	9.5	1.05	7.9	3.9	10.9	5.7	1.60	10.3	37.25	0.62	33	84
47–56	Bw3	0.22	2.59	20.4	68.6	11.0	0.30	7.7	4.2	11.5	7.8	2.35	10.5	40.20	0.68	38	127
56–66	Bw4	0.22	2.99	8.1	75.4	16.5	0.11	7.8	6.2	12.6	7.1	1.90	8.95	41.65	0.75	42	105
66–90	C	0.11	2.59	14.7	73.3	12.0	0.20	7.6	6.4	10.2	7.3	1.85	9.60	43.10	0.71	44	90
(P4) Boritika series – Fluvaquentic Endoaquepts																	
0–26	Ap	0.11	2.37	29.4	46.6	24.0	0.63	7.0	12.3	17.9	10.9	3.45	3.8	36.2	0.58	36	87
26–52	C1	0.11	2.37	77.5	16.5	6.0	4.69	7.5	1.6	11.9	4.2	2.00	4.5	23.4	0.36	18	53
52–64	2Bw1	0.11	2.70	13.3	52.2	34.5	0.25	7.2	11.0	19.6	8.9	2.35	3.0	36.5	0.42	44	88
64–79	2Bw2	0.22	2.26	17.1	53.4	29.5	0.33	7.3	4.3	20.0	8.0	2.50	3.2	38.9	0.43	49	90
79–115	C2	0.22	2.26	92.5	1.0	6.5	92.5	7.6	0.6	8.89	3.3	1.55	4.2	18.8	0.36	8	36

Foot note : C1 = hue index, C2 = chroma index, OC = organic carbon, CEC = cation exchange capacity.

regime and its erratic distribution with depth indicates sediment layering due to fluvial deposition. The organic carbon content of 0.2% below 125 cm and irregular distribution with depth of 25 to 125 cm is considered for classifying at subgroup level in the orders of entisol and inceptisols as Humaqueptic Fluvaquents (Kamalabari series, P1), Fluventic Endoaqupts (Sonaribari series, P3), Fluvaquentic Endoaqupts (Boritika series, P4) and Typic Endoaqupts (Adielengi series, P2). These soils have low cation exchange capacity 3.5 cmol/kg in C horizons of P2 to 20 cmol/kg in 2Bw2 (P4) due to destruction of silicate clay during ferrolysis³⁴ causing replacement of exchangeable bases by Fe²⁺ upon the onset of reduced conditions. Under oxidized conditions, iron gets precipitated and produces H⁺ that causes charge reduction and loss of Al³⁺ from octahedral layer. Under reduced conditions, ferrous iron affects the development of the rice crop in two ways : (i) by coating the plant roots with iron oxide and thus reducing the absorption capacity of the plant for other nutrients, such as P, K, Ca, and Mg (Fe*+-induced deficiency), or (ii) by direct iron toxicity through excessive Fe*+ absorption by the plant with characteristic orange discoloration³⁷. The cation exchange capacity is positively and significantly related with organic carbon (0.63**) and clay (0.86**) and expressed in regression equation as :

- $CEC(\text{cmol}(\text{p}^+)\text{kg}^{-1}) = 0.853(\text{organic carbon}(\text{g}/\text{kg})) - 3.99$
- $CEC(\text{cmol}(\text{p}^+)\text{kg}^{-1}) = 2.15 (\text{clay } \%) - 10.35$

Elemental composition : The elemental composition

of hydric soils of Majuli island is presented in Table 1. The total K content shows gradational decrease in all soils with its weighted mean of 1.85 g/kg in P1 and 6.47 g/kg in P4. The striking differences in distribution of Ca in P1 (weighted mean of 2.91 g/kg) and in P3 (9.32 g/kg) point out the susceptibility to leaching and rapid weathering of calcic minerals in soils³⁸ whereas total Fe and Mn contents are low in soils on old flood plains (P2) and active flood plains (P1) and channel fills (P4) indicating loss of Fe and Mn through ground water flow (lateral runoff) and enriching gleyzation processes¹⁰ in the B horizons with Fe (40.2 g/kg P3 and 38.9 g/kg P4) and Mn (0.751 g/kg in 4 P3 and 0.81 g/kg in P2) at an observed redox potential of E_H, 170 mV²⁵. The Cu content in Sonaribari series (P3) vary from 33 to 50 mg/kg with decreasing trend upto 47 cm but increases to 44 mg/kg at C horizons. The C horizons have Cu content less than 10 mg/kg in P2 and P4. The horizon wise distribution of Cu in Kamalabari series shows decreasing trend from 28 to 14 mg/kg but irregular in other soils. The Zn content is more than 100 mg/kg in P1 and in P3 but less in P2 and P4 with irregular depth trends. The lack of definite trends of Cu and Zn lends an indirect support of high degree of profile differentiation in soil profiles²⁰.

Clay-elemental masses : The clay mass in C horizons of old flood plains (P2) is 51 to 98 kg/m² but low in cambic horizons of natural levees (P3, 13.1 to 18.1 kg/m², Table 2). The mass of K, Ca, Cu and Zn is low with the pedogenic modification due to regular deposition of

Table 2. Clay and elemental contents in the hydric soils

Depth (cm)	Horizon	Clay	K	Ca	Fe (kg/m ²)	Mn	Cu	Zn	Bulk density (Mg m ³)
<i>(P1) Kamalabari series – Humaqueptic fluvaquents</i>									
0-19	Ap	49.8	0.89	0.71	7.89	0.08	0.007	0.029	1.6
19-39	AC	44.2	0.48	0.56	8.89	0.10	0.007	0.029	1.7
39-61	C1	22.0	0.57	1.01	10.07	0.16	0.008	0.037	1.3
61-89	C2	34.3	0.68	1.21	12.54	0.19	0.011	0.044	1.4
89-130	C3	27.9	0.81	1.98	14.30	0.25	0.008	0.074	1.7
<i>(P2) Adielengi – Typic Endoaqupts</i>									
0-13	Ap	21.3	1.70	1.65	7.42	0.12	0.007	0.015	1.49
13-34	Bw1	88.7	3.74	0.97	11.85	0.19	0.011	0.025	1.28
34-60	Bw2	71.5	3.20	1.40	14.13	0.28	0.015	0.028	1.31
60-98	C1	51.6	2.24	2.12	16.35	0.32	0.013	0.032	1.51
98-225	C2	97.79	4.11	5.10	28.55	0.51	0.009	0.059	1.54

(P3) Sonaribari series – Fluventic Endoauepts									
0-13	Ap	65.9	2.05	1.12	8.62	0.12	0.011	0.019	1.47
13-31	B/A	55.7	2.89	2.82	12.37	0.21	0.013	0.027	1.51
31-38	Bw1	13.1	0.73	0.95	4.02	0.07	0.004	0.008	1.39
38-47	Bw2	11.0	0.66	1.21	4.34	0.07	0.003	0.009	1.29
47-56	Bw3	13.2	0.93	1.26	4.81	0.08	0.005	0.015	1.33
56-66	Bw4	18.8	0.81	1.03	4.75	0.08	0.005	0.012	1.14
66-90	C	36.3	2.21	2.90	13.03	0.22	0.013	0.027	1.26
(P4) Boritika series – Fluvaquentic Endoauepts									
0-26	Ap	82.4	3.74	1.30	12.42	0.19	0.012	0.029	1.32
26-52	C1	24.8	1.74	1.86	9.67	0.15	0.007	0.022	1.59
52-64	2Bw1	50.5	1.30	0.44	5.34	0.06	0.006	0.013	1.22
64-79	2Bw2	56.2	1.52	0.61	7.41	0.08	0.009	0.017	1.27
79-113	C2	23.4	1.19	1.51	6.78	0.13	0.003	0.013	1.06

alluvium with striking profile distribution of K and Ca in P1 and P3. The enrichment of Fe and Mn mass in these soils shows positive relation with hue index (Fe $r = 0.43^*$ and Mn 0.42^*) but negative with chroma index (Fe $r = -0.32$ and Mn -0.42^*). The total Fe is positively and significantly related with clay (0.63^{**}) and organic carbon (0.63^{**}). Similar findings were reported in Indo-Gangetic plains of Punjab²⁰ and in paddy growing soils of Brahmaputra valley^{1,15}.

Cluster analysis : The average linkage method was employed to workout chemical affinity of soil horizons and derived four clusters. The cluster-1 includes 8 horizon sequences as cambic B horizons of Sonaribari (P3), Ap horizon of Adielengi (P2) have strong affinity with C1 horizons of Kamalabari (P1) and Boritika (P4) whereas in cluster-2 has strong affinity between C horizons of P1 and P3, cluster-3 with B and C horizons of P2 and Ap and AC horizons of P1 and in cluster-4 between B horizons of P2 and Ap horizons of P3 and P4. The cluster analysis shows the degree and kind of associations between the array of horizon sequences if arranged may clearly indicate the mode of deposition of alluvium in bringing out the pedogenic differentiation in soils. It is further evident from the mean mass of clay in cluster-3 (52.1 kg/m^2) with per cent of variation of 9.2% as against in cluster-4 with mean clay of 81.26 kg/m^2 and per cent coefficient of variation of 15.82 (Table 3). Likewise,

the mean mass of K (3.36 kg/m^2), Ca (1.98 kg/m^2), Fe (15.14 kg/m^2) and Mn (0.26 kg/m^2) shows more than 50% of variation in cluster-4.

Losses and gains of elements : The relative changes of P ratios compared with the C ratios result in huge losses of elements under extreme reductive conditions in C (Table 4). Adielengi series on old flood plains (P2) has shown the enrichment of K and Cu throughout profile with net gain of 25% for K and 136% of Cu with slight loss of Ca (28%), Fe (19.4%), Mn (13.5%) and Zn (17.4%). In P3, little gains of K, Ca, Fe, Mn and Zn in Bw horizons at 38 to 56 cm are helpful to differentiate and identify the biserial depositions in soils on channel fills. Severe loss of K, Ca, Fe, Mn and Zn elements in soils on old flood plains (P4) is due to intense leaching and low amount of mass added to profiles. The little losses of elements in P2 and P3 shows the less period of saturation as compared to (reducing conditions < 40% of time) severe losses in P1 and P4 (> 90% of reducing time). This is in agreement of findings reported in wetland soils of Allagu region in South West Germany²⁵. The enrichment of Fe and Mn in old flood plains indicates low break down of minerals and leaching of cations under neutral environment¹⁰. It is interesting to note that the Ap horizons in P2 has shown net gains of all elements indicating enrichment of elements in young alluvium.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of clay-elemental masses in hydric soils

Descriptive statistics	Clay	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn	Bulk density (Mg m ³)
	(kg/m ²)							
Cluster-1								
Mean	18.45	1.04	1.31	6.48	0.11	0.005	0.016	1.32
SD	5.31	0.46	0.33	2.40	0.04	0.002	0.009	0.17
CV (%)	28.77	44.07	25.29	37.08	34.36	36.35	57.28	13.02
Cluster-2								
Mean	32.16	0.72	1.46	13.12	0.21	0.01	0.054	1.50
SD	3.69	0.08	0.44	1.01	0.03	0.002	0.017	0.173
CV (%)	11.48	10.37	30.31	7.74	16.49	17.32	32.075	11.55
Cluster-3								
Mean	52.1	1.43	0.96	8.22	0.10	0.008	0.022	1.43
SD	4.83	0.82	0.92	2.34	0.054	0.0025	0.007	0.20
CV (%)	9.27	57.18	95.60	28.48	53.66	29.52	32.39	14.12
Cluster-4								
Mean	81.26	3.36	1.98	15.14	0.26	0.011	0.032	1.38
SD	12.85	0.81	1.75	7.77	0.15	0.002	0.015	0.11
CV (%)	15.82	23.90	88.62	51.42	58.87	18.88	48.71	8.25

Foot note : SD = standard deviation, CV = coefficient of variation.

Table 4. Per cent losses and gains of elementals in hydric soils

Depth (cm)	Horizon	K	Ca	Fe	Mn	Cu	Zn
(P1) Kamalabari series – Humaqueptic fluvaquepts							
0–19	Ap	-37.9	-79.8	-69.1	-81.62	-52.6	-78.3
19–39	AC	-62.1	82.1	-60.73	-74.1	-43.4	-74.9
39–61	C1	-10.6	-35.6	-10.7	-17.9	+24.31	-35.6
61–89	C2	-30.6	-50.4	-28.7	-36.44	-5.4	-51.4
Net gain/loss (%)		-35.32	-61.9	-42.3	-52.5	-19.3	-60.1
(P2) Adielengi–Typic – Endoaquepts							
0–13	Ap	+90.47	+49.32	+19.22	+11.7	+255.3	+16.74
13–34	Bw1	0	-78.9	-54.1	-59.3	+26.75	-52.7
34–60	Bw2	+7.14	-62.4	-43.2	-25.9	+07.6	-35.6
60–98	C1	+2.38	-20.8	+8.5	+19.4	+155.6	+2.0
Net gain/loss (%)		+24.94	-28.3	-19.4	-13.5	+136.4	-17.4
(P3) Sonaribari series – Fluventic Endoaquepts							
0–13	Ap	-48.8	-78.6	-63.6	-68.3	-56.6	-61.3
13–31	B/A	-14.5	-36.6	-38.2	-37.3	-36.24	-34.9
31–38	Bw1	-8.4	-8.9	-14.4	-10.8	-15.0	-10.82
38–47	Bw2	-1.0	+37.3	+9.9	+10.6	-5.2	+12.6
47–56	Bw3	+16.4	+19.1	+1.5	+4.2	-6.1	+57.2
56–66	Bw4	-29.2	-31.8	-29.6	-23.1	-27.3	-11.0
Net gain/loss (%)		-14.3	-16.6	-22.4	-20.8	+24.4	-8.1
(P4) Boritika series – Fluvaqueptic Endoaquepts							
0–26	Ap	-12	-76.92	-47.75	-56.1	+20.9	-35.7
26–52	C1	+37	+15.38	+34.94	+17.64	+140.0	+58.91
52–64	2Bw1	-51	-86.6	-63.3	-70.6	+2.4	-53.9
64–79	2Bw2	-47	-83.1	-54.33	-73.5	+33.1	-46.1
Net gain/loss (%)		-18.13	-57.8	-32.6	-45.1	+41.0	-19.1

Conclusions :

Four hydric soils in alluvial sequence on southern bank of Majuli river island showed progressive loss of clay and coarsening of texture due to ferrollysis as controlled by alternate oxidation and reduction. The Adielengi (P2) on old flood plains and Sonaribari (P3) on natural levees show little losses of elements as compared to soils on active flood plains (P1) and Boritika (P4) on channel fills. The geochemical data sets were helpful to trace out the depositional episodes as evident from thickening of B horizons with moderately low saturated hydraulic conductivity in Adielengi and Sonaribari soils. The prolonged seasonal submergence of soils promotes potassium and Zn deficiency for rice production. At landscape level, texture exerts influence on water movement and iron dynamics emphasizing on supplementary agronomic measure of application K and increasing concentrations of iron favours deficiency of manganese to succeeding crops in the region.

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